

METHODOLOGY OF TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES

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Abstract: After our country gained independence, Uzbekistan began to build a democratic life from the first years of independence. The economy was also important. The weight of the implemented reforms increased from year to year. Not only fundamental reforms, but many changes have taken place in other aspects, including in the education system. In particular, interest in teaching foreign languages has increased and many conditions have been created for young people. The main goal of this is to increase the level of knowledge of young people and increase their interest in foreign languages. The goal of this article is to teach the young generation through new and interesting methods of teaching a foreign language.

Keywords: Pedagogical communication , Language learning , special names , , a method , psychological knowledge

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Language learning is one of the most important areas in human society. Language, which is a means of communication, can be acquired practically in a natural environment, i.e. in the family, in the community or in an organized manner. Knowledge of language phenomena is taught theoretically. Knowledge of languages, especially multilingualism, is of great importance in our time of increased international relations. Pupils and students studying in our country usually study three languages. These languages are referred to by special names. These are: mother tongue, second language, and foreign language. The mother tongue is the first language that plays a special role in the formation of thinking. When talking about the second language, it is considered as the language of brothers and neighbors of other nationalities.

A foreign language is the language of a foreign country. Western European languages (English, Spanish, German, French) and Eastern languages (Arabic, Turkish, Persian, Chinese, Indian) are taught in our republic. These languages are included in the curricula of educational institutions. The process of teaching all three languages is different. The mother tongue and the second language are learned in a natural situation, and a foreign language is learned in an artificial environment. Communication in a foreign language mainly takes place in the classroom under the guidance of the teacher. Among the three languages, learning and teaching a foreign language differs sharply in certain aspects. This, in turn,

requires the use of appropriate foreign language teaching technology. By carefully mastering the achievements of the methodical science, the foreign language teacher will be able to clearly know the standard of language experience of the student and to improve it further. Effective teaching of foreign languages requires knowledge of its methodology. Learning and teaching foreign languages in many ways involves the issues of foreign language teaching methodology from a theoretical point of view.

depends on the development and creative application of the theory in practice.

The subject of the methodology is the process and methods of education through the subject of a foreign language, the science of teaching a foreign language, the study of teacher and student activity is considered the subject of the methodology.

The main concepts of methodology - method, method, principle. Didactics - what do we teach? is the content of teaching. Methodology - how do we teach? means educational methods and methods. The concept of method - methodology is derived from the Greek-Latin word "methodos-"methodus" and means ways leading to a certain goal, a method. In various literature, you can find the narrow and broad meaning of the term. "Methodology The term " in a narrow sense refers to the concept of education related to the concrete lesson process. It is interpreted as a controlled lesson process that includes instructions related to the planning of lessons and the preparation of educational materials. "Method The term "in a broad sense refers to the selection, classification and distribution of educational material. In the Federal Republic of Germany, since the 1960s, "didactics" and "methodology" have been used in a narrow sense. Accordingly, the content of didactic education What is taught? Methodology deals with the issues of how educational methods are taught. Learning foreign languages is not only a means of intellectual education, but also an opportunity to get acquainted with the educational resources and values of a foreign culture and learn them. z from It is the process of forming a person's personality by applying it to his life. In Europe, the study of foreign languages has long been considered a privilege in higher education, and public schools are seen as educating the privileged few. The term intercultural communication is widely used in foreign language teaching methodology. It is this concept that we can apply in many different contexts. In fact: Intercultural communication is communication-information about the social origin, mentality, national character, way of life, customs, value system, etc. of representatives of different cultures. In this process, it is necessary to educate and develop students in the spirit of respect, patience and correct understanding of the culture of the country they are studying.

Every foreign language lesson is a cultural intersection, a practice of intercultural communication. Because every foreign language word in this process reflects foreign life and culture. The task before teachers is to develop the ability of pupils and students to communicate. For this, it is necessary to learn new methods of education aimed at developing the four speech activities in a foreign language, teaching manuals that teach people to communicate effectively.

The formula of intercultural communication is patience and tolerance. It is necessary to avoid socio-cultural mistakes in intercultural communication. For example, in German people, "Tee oder Kaffee?" that is, we answer the question "tea or coffee" in our native language with "Tee", "tea", but in German, such an answer is not appropriate. In German, the answer is "Bitte, Tee", that is, "Thank you, tea". Words connect people through communication. As a result of using the new material simultaneously in all types of speech activity

skills and abilities are created. In this process, the quality and effectiveness of education will increase if communication tools, demonstration, types of modern technology, methods, and the principle of consistency are provided.

In order to successfully work, a teacher-teacher needs not only subject, pedagogical and psychological knowledge, but also other special features - communication skills and qualifications.

A person begins to acquire communication skills from infancy. But after growing up, not everyone can communicate as well as they should. By its nature, the profession of pedagogy belongs to the professions of the "human-human" type, and that is why the ability to communicate is considered one of the leading and important professional skills for a pedagogue. interest in the subject of study, therefore, study motives are formed. Pedagogical communication method affects the students' subject knowledge, results of skills, culture of interpersonal relations, creates a unique moral-psychological climate in the educational process. Communication is an important condition for socialization of a person. At this point, it is necessary to know what pedagogical communication actually is.

Pedagogical communication is a mutual cooperation between a teacher and a student, which is based on the exchange of information, first of all educational information, helps to understand the partner of pedagogical communication, as well as to implement mutual cooperation activities. In this case, information is conveyed both verbally, that is, through speech, and non-verbally - through means. In the process of pedagogical communication, the teacher should play the main role and be an example for students. This is evaluated by his communicative culture.

The communicative culture of the teacher is a professional-pedagogical dialogue with the subjects of the educational process. As a necessary level of communicative culture, it can be defined that the teacher can positively accept his

students and colleagues, and education and upbringing can definitely ensure the achievement of its goals.

Learning a foreign language is a multifaceted discipline, in which a person undergoes complex psychological changes. In particular, the process of comparing the native language with a foreign language occurs. Various teaching methods and technologies are used in this process. With the help of modern pedagogical technologies, teaching by comparing the foreign language with the mother tongue gives an effective result. Teaching a foreign language requires knowledge of its methodology. Methodology and technologies are important in the process of learning a foreign language. There are various methods of teaching methodology. The widely used methods in foreign language teaching methodology are: communicative didactic method, intercultural dialogue organization method and exercise organization method. All three methods are closely related and complement each other. Practice is the best way to master all knowledge. The exercise gives a positive result not only in foreign language education, but also in mastering knowledge in all fields. Effective organization of the lesson, the role of the pedagogue and modern pedagogical technologies in it is incomparable. It is important to organize the process of learning a foreign language with a communicative approach, to bring the next level to the level of intercultural communication, and to achieve such results, it is important to pay attention to the last step, "exercise technology". Teaching a foreign language

in order to effectively organize the process, it is necessary to acquire knowledge of modern pedagogical information and communication technologies.

In reforming the education system of our republic, coordination with educational programs based on foreign experiences and meeting international standards became the basis for improving the higher pedagogical education system. Under the conditions of Uzbekistan, taking into account our national mentality and traditions, the fundamental reform of the quality of education on the basis of foreign experiences is the need of the hour. In this regard, in the Strategy of Actions on the five priority directions of the development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021, it is stated in our country, "...increasing the quality and efficiency of the activities of higher education institutions, scientific stimulating research and innovative activities, creating effective mechanisms for implementing scientific and innovative achievements...", increasing the quality of personnel training, creating the necessary conditions for training qualified specialists based on international standards, each higher education institution is the world's leading scientific and establishing close cooperative relations with educational institutions and developing students' creative abilities, effectively using interactive methods in working with young audiences, being able to provide them with quality education

in a foreign language, bringing the level of higher education to an exemplary level and fundamentally Therefore, in the process of producing future personnel in the higher education system of our republic and finding information necessary for scientific purposes, reading original literature on the specialty, participating in oral communication in a foreign language Foreign language classes are being held in order to form a culture.

Every citizen of the independent Republic of Uzbekistan should be able to read the original copy of foreign language literature related to his profession, understand the read text and be able to apply it in his profession. In addition, he should be able to freely exchange ideas with the interlocutor in a foreign language on the given topic. After all, learning foreign languages is a requirement of today's globalized era.

In our country, with the honor of independence, special attention is paid to the teaching of foreign languages. Thousands of foreign language teachers have been trained, all conditions have been created for personnel to improve their skills in our motherland and abroad, multimedia textbooks in English, German, French, electronic resources for learning English have been prepared, modern educational institutions the establishment of language rooms is a clear proof of this. The goals of teaching a foreign language are determined based on the demands of society, social orders, conditions, and policies. The goals of foreign language teaching depend on the progress and development of society. Teaching a foreign language in higher educational institutions has its own goals, and all foreign language teachers should define it in advance. After all, as scientists O. Hoshimov and I. Yakubov said in the book "Methodology of English Language Teaching", "the goals of foreign language teaching determine the content, means, methods, and principles of teaching."

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